

Interventions with omega-3 fatty acids on inflammatory diseases in critically ill newborns: Opportunities to improve their clinical outcomes

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ABSTRACT 150 words.

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The omega fatty acids such as docosahexaenoic acid, have immunomodulatory and antiinflammatory effects. These are particularly important in newborns who often present complications that involve inflammatory diseases. However, this intervention has been scarcely studied in this vulnerable population. Here, we review the beneficial effects of the enteral DHA in critically ill term and preterm newborns that underwent systemic inflammatory response or local inflammatory diseases as a feasible strategy to improve their clinical outcomes.

Key words: DHA; omega-3 fatty acids; neonate; premature infant, inflammatory disease.

Introduction.

Fat or lipids are mainly known due to their role in our diet to supply energy. Fatty acids are the components of lipids. One type of those lipids are known as the long-chain polyunsaturated fatty acids Omega 3 (n3 LC-PUFA), such as docosahexaenoic acid (DHA) and eicosapentaenoic acid (EPA), which can be contained in oily fish, some algae, fortified eggs and meat. These n3 LC-PUFA have demonstrated being crucial for retina and cognitive development, immunomodulatory effects, also to reduce inflammation, oxidative stress, among others in experimental models and humans (Lapillone et al. 2017; Calder, 2018; Huun, 2018). However, the omega-3 effects depend on the dose and duration of the omega 3 administration, the fatty acid profile and inflammatory status of the patients, the presence of genetic variants of some enzymes to use them as substrates, etc., to be able to demonstrate clinical benefits Calder, 2017).

The term and preterm newborn have reduced ability to synthesise n3 LC-PUFA from its precursor, the alpha-linolenic acid (Martin et al. 2015). Thus, they must receive them through their feeding or parenteral nutrition. However, preterm infants did not have the opportunity to accrete them during the last trimester of gestation. Therefore, they have greater requirements and frequent DHA deficiency compared with term newborns. The immaturity of all systems and above mentioned factors may predispose them to inflammatory complications during their hospitalization (Martin et al. 2015).

Mortality rate in newborns had little improvement since 2000 due to 7000 babies die every day in the first 28 days of life (neonatal period), despite steady decrease in under-five mortality worldwide. The proportion of under-five deaths in the newborn period has increased from 41% to 46% (WHO, 2017). Therefore, this represents a challenge and research in this population should be addressed to end preventable complications that increase their mortality risk. Therefore, we consider that omega 3 fatty acids may give us opportunities to use them as interventions for treatment or prevention of diseases in critically ill newborns.

Results of our research supplementing DHA to critically ill newborns

Our double blinded clinical trials have demonstrated that the administration of enteral DHA in infants with pneumonia and exposed to a quadruple vaccination did reduced circulating inflammatory cytokines which increase during inflammation processes, but also are responsible of the appetite loss when infants are sick. Thus, infants who received DHA reduced less their appetite compared with controls (López-Alarcon et al. 2002, López-Alarcon et al. 2006, López-Alarcon et al. 2008). In another study in term newborns who received the DHA during the acute phase of sepsis, it ameliorated the catabolic effect of cytokines as inflammatory mediators, increased the weight gain compared with baseline and increased the body fat as the energy reserves in newborns after 14 days of supplementation compared with the loss in body composition in control group (Lopez-Alarcon et al. 2006). In these patients, the DHA reduced the circulating levels of IL-1beta, an inflammatory cytokine responsible for the catabolic effect. In addition, DHA was significantly incorporated into white cell membranes, and this incorporation predicted positive changes in illness severity (Lopez-Alarcon et al. 2012). In other study, newborns who underwent a cardiovascular surgery received enteral DHA before the surgery (before of the inflammatory stimulus). The DHA reduced the elevation of intracellular inflammatory cytokines and caused an early elevation of intracellular anti-inflammatory cytokines, leading to a significant reduction of the development of organ dysfunctions and reducing 4.5 days the stay in the neonatal intensive care unit (NICU) (Bernabe-Garcia et al. 2016). In those babies, the DHA resulted in a reduction in the cumulative dose and duration of buprenorphine received during their NICU stay compared with controls (Bernabe-Garcia et al. 2016). Buprenorphine is an opioid used as pain treatment, and it is also known that inflammatory cytokines are pain mediators. As DHA reduced them, these suggests that also may reduce pain.

On the other hand, preterm infants born with deficiency of DHA. It is deposited during the last trimester, mainly in brain and retina with a prominent role in cognition and visual acuity. In preterm infants, the organ immaturity, inflammation and oxygen supply lead to the development of Retinopathy of the Prematurity (ROP). Nearly 190,000 preterm neonates develop some stage of ROP, from those approximately 20,000 become blind each year (Benclowe et al, 2010). In Latin America is the major cause of childhood blindness (Furtado et al.

2012). We administrated enteral DHA to newborns with weight at birth less than 1500 g and found that the severe ROP was prevented. This is relevant because it may progress to retina detachment (sent to publication).

Conclusions. Omega 3 fatty acids such as DHA may be an strategy to reduce the risk and severity of the inflammatory complications in critically ill newborns.

Future work

We need more studies with higher sample sizes in different hospital settings (developed, emerging and developing countries) to confirm the beneficial effects of this strategy. This could be possible through collaborations among health institution and universities.

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